

POLITICAL SCIENCES

STRATEGIC GOALS IN HEYDAR ALIYEV'S EDUCATION POLICY: FORMATION OF NATIONAL PERSONNEL

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Abstract

The article analyzes the science and education policy implemented by Heydar Aliyev during the Soviet period and the years of independence, and the concept of education, which he founded. In accordance with the set goal, issues such as the priority of education in the Soviet era and the strengthening of national personnel potential, education policy and its integration into the world education system during the period of independence, the concept of education and its positive results were studied and analyzed. The main focus is on the role played by Heydar Aliyev in the development of national education, training of national personnel, the opening of military lyceum, secondary and higher schools, the sending of Azerbaijani youth to the most prestigious universities in the world, and its positive results for current education.

Keywords: Heydar Aliyev, science and education policy, national education, training of military personnel, Education Concept of independent Azerbaijan.

Introduction

Society is a synthesis of personalities and society, society members. A person who can lead the community becomes a great personality and becomes the author of ideas and the driving force of the processes. However, even the most beautiful, progressive idea in itself is not enough for social progress. The realization of the idea is the main condition. In order for the society to move towards the social ideal, it is enough to achieve the society's confidence in the personality and the leader. Again, the main task falls on the personality. The bitter tragedy of abandonment or loneliness awaits those who cannot gain or justify their faith. Thus, it can be said with complete certainty that it is the personalities that develop the society. [Musayev, 2023].

From this point of view, the development of the field of education was one of the priority directions in the strategy of the great leader Heydar Aliyev aimed at the future of the people of Azerbaijan. The reforms carried out in this direction covered all levels of education and the material and technical base. The educational reforms carried out in Azerbaijan under the leadership of Heydar Aliyev since the 70s of the last century constitute a special stage in the development of this field. Educational reforms carried out during the first period of Heydar Aliyev's leadership in Azerbaijan laid the foundation for the development of this field. As a result of the implementation of the decisions adopted in 1972 "On completing the transition of young people to general secondary education and further developing the general education school" and in 1973 "On further improving the working conditions of rural general education schools", the network of secondary schools in the republic was expanded, fundamentally

qualitative change was achieved. Also, the problem of providing schools with textbooks was solved, and starting from 1978, textbooks were given to students free of charge [AZERTAC, 2022].

In the educational policy of the genius leader, further improvement of the activity of higher schools and strengthening of their material and technical base had a special place. On November 1, 1969, Heydar Aliyev, who participated in the solemn meeting dedicated to the 50th anniversary of Baku State University, spoke about the tasks ahead in the field of higher education in his speech in his native language. This was a turning point in the direction of the awakening of the national spirit not only for the university staff, but for the entire Azerbaijani society.

One of the main issues that concerned Heydar Aliyev was the preparation of Azerbaijani youth for the army and their involvement in military schools. As a result of his initiative and foresight, a military-oriented school named after Jamshid Nakhchivanski was established in 1971.

1. Prioritization of education and strengthening of national personnel potential in the Soviet era

The statesman who prepared the ground for the future independence of Azerbaijan in 1969-1982 did great work in the direction of its revival by preventing the suppression of the national spirit and Azerbaijaniness within the framework of the Soviet ideology. The Great Leader skillfully used the available opportunities and said that life is a big process. In order to successfully participate in this process, a person must have an education in accordance with modern requirements.

"The field of education is the most important field for the future of our people, our nation, our state", - the decisions taken by the Great Leader, who always highly appreciates the role of education in the development of society and its importance in the formation of personality, conceptual ideas and ideas put forward with foresight, and historical recommendations are still valid today. contributes to defining the main directions of educational reforms in our country. The wise leader, who did great work for the development of Azerbaijani education, did not look at education only as an opportunity to gain knowledge and learn science, he always emphasized that education has an important role in the formation of an active citizen's position and close participation in the process of progress in society [Karimzadeh, 2019].

The national leader was well aware of how important this issue is for Azerbaijan to be recognized among countries and states, and to gain prestige. That is why he attached great importance to the youth's higher education, education, and acquisition of fundamental and humanitarian sciences. At the same time, he kept in mind the solution of the problems hindering the progress of science and education, and in this direction, he set the important task of strengthening the intellectual resources of the republic and strengthening the educational infrastructure. The construction and modernization of new buildings for schools, higher and secondary specialized institutions on a large scale, the implementation of certain projects for the purpose of training qualified personnel was a clear expression of this [Bagirov, 2022].

July 14, 1969, which is the turning stage of modern Azerbaijan, entered our national history as the beginning of a great era led by Heydar Aliyev, and the historical stage that started from that year is valued as the renaissance period of Azerbaijani education, science and culture. From the very first day, the genius personality who defied all the ideological and political barriers of the Soviet regime and led the society to progress in all directions, considered it an extremely important factor for the strengthening of the national ideology in the society and the re-formation of the consciousness of statehood for every Azerbaijani to receive a higher education and master scientific innovations. Under the leadership of the Great Leader, successive measures were taken in the direction of the nationalization of education, the development of our language, and the preservation of the historical nature of social sciences.

In that period, all educational institutions in Azerbaijan rose to a new level of development compared to previous years, and the consistent state policy in this direction played an exceptional role in raising the educational, general cultural and intellectual level of the population of Azerbaijan [Bayramov, 2019].

In that period, special attention to the development of education was also shown in school construction. In 1979, the number of secondary schools more than tripled to 2117 compared to 1965, and in 1982 it reached 4267. The number of students increased from 368 thousand in 1970 to 710 thousand in 1980. In 1970-

1980, 1191 new school buildings with a capacity of 683.1 thousand students were built and put into use in the republic, which was twice as much as the corresponding indicator in 1946-1970.

During the first period of Heydar Aliyev's leadership in Azerbaijan, the number of vocational schools increased by 1.7 times compared to 1965, and the number of students increased by 2.5 times. On his initiative, a strategy for the improvement and development of technical vocational education was determined for the years 1971-1975, 54 new technical vocational education institutions started to operate.

Emphasizing the important role of the university in the life of the Azerbaijani people and in the development of Azerbaijani science, Heydar Aliyev said: "In 1919, when the issue of opening a university was discussed in the public circles of Azerbaijan, some doubted and said that this work would not be done. It is better to educate young people in well-known university centers of foreign countries. send to buy. Today, we can tell those unbelievers that ambassadors from four continents are coming to Azerbaijan to study" [AZERTAC, 2022].

In 1969-1982, when national leader Heydar Aliyev led Azerbaijan, five new higher education institutions were opened and the number of higher education students increased from 70,000 to 100,000. If at the end of the 1960s, there were 105 faculties and 450 departments in 12 higher schools in the republic and personnel training was being conducted in 139 specialties, in 1982 there were already 21 higher education institutions combining 136 faculties and 530 departments.

One of the exceptional services of Heydar Aliyev in the development of education in Azerbaijan is the creation of national personnel potential, including a contingent of specialists in rare specialties. For this purpose, he created conditions for more than 15,000 Azerbaijani youths to study in more than 170 prestigious higher schools of more than 50 major cities of the former USSR outside of Azerbaijan, and in the future, more than 80 areas of our republic's economy, science, education and culture. , made a great contribution to meeting the need for highly qualified personnel in more than 250 specialties [Aliyev, 2023].

In 1982-1987, when Heydar Aliyev was the first deputy chairman of the Council of Ministers of the USSR, he created conditions for the youth of Azerbaijan to study outside the borders of the republic. He often met with Azerbaijani students and used all opportunities to solve their problems. He appreciated them as "children of Azerbaijan, national wealth of Azerbaijan".

Hundreds of Azerbaijani citizens began to study at the Jamshid Nakhchivanski military-oriented high school created as a result of his initiative. The Great Leader had great respect for those who devoted their lives to military art and the profession of officers and always appreciated their services. The formation of modern professional officer cadres, without a doubt, actualized the level of organization of education in military educational institutions of the country. The development of the institutional foundations of the

education system, the expansion of the application of innovative training methods and technologies, the creation of a competency-based personality and result-oriented education model have been set as a strategic goal. Based on this principle, we can say that the steps taken at that time are bearing fruit today [Huseynov, 2022: 25].

That is, Jamshid Nakhchivanski Military Lyceum had an exceptional role in the training of national officers and in the formation of our Armed Forces. Today, most of the officers serving in the ranks of our army are graduates of Jamshid Nakhchivanski Military High School. They showed great skill and bravery in the battles for the freedom of our lands.

At the same time, not only within the country, but also in the 70s and 80s of the last century, under the leadership of Heydar Aliyev, the creation of a wide network of educational institutions and the formation of a rich material and technical base of that network, the sending of Azerbaijani youth to study at universities outside the borders of the republic, the training of military personnel, ensuring the development of fundamental science in the research institutes of the Republican Academy of Sciences created the necessary intellectual ground for national independence in the future [AZERTAC, 2022].

2. Education policy in the period of independence and integration into the world education system

Since coming to power, i.e., starting from 1993, one of the priority areas that the state gave importance to was the education policy. Heydar Aliyev, who returned to the leadership in a very difficult situation of the republic, besides solving many problems, began to implement reforms in the field of education in accordance with the requirements of the time. In 1991-1993, the disturbed activity of educational institutions was brought to a normal state, and the basis of planned reforms was laid. The number of secondary schools and the number of students increased substantially. If in 1993-1994 academic year 1 million 549 thousand students studied in 4364 general education schools of the republic, in 2002-2003 academic year more than 1 million 600 thousand teenagers continued their education in 4561 general education schools.

In addition, the material and technical base of the education system was improved, 200 new school buildings were built and put into use, and more than 700 general education schools were established in the regions and cities where IDPs temporarily live. About 30 lyceums and gymnasiums were organized in order to develop the abilities of talented children, and about 12 thousand students were involved here.

"After deeply studying the current state of our education system and its problems, priority areas should be determined," said the Great Leader, who has done important work in Azerbaijan for the implementation of an education strategy in accordance with the experience of developed countries of the world. On March 30, 1998, the State Commission for Education Reforms was established by the President's Decree, "Education Reform Program of the Republic of Azerbaijan" was prepared and approved on June 15,

1999. [URL, 1999]. In the program, by determining the future development strategy of education, fundamental reforms were planned in the structure, management, content, material and technical base, economy, personnel training and provision of the education system.

"On improving the education system of the Republic of Azerbaijan" June 13, 2000, "On improving the implementation of the state language" June 18, 2001, "On establishing the Azerbaijan Alphabet and Azerbaijani Language Day" August 9, 2001, "Azerbaijan Decrees dated January 2, 2003 "On the implementation of the Law on the state language in the Republic of Azerbaijan" [President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2024]. played a big role in raising our education to world standards. At the same time, attention was paid to the teaching of Azerbaijani history, literature, geography, the preparation of excellent textbooks, the teaching of the Azerbaijani language, especially its promotion as a state language.

The reforms did not cover only educational institutions, fundamental work was also done to encourage young people to study. The Decree dated September 3, 2001 on establishing the Presidential scholarship for higher school students is a clear example of this.

Reconstruction and improvement of the education system in the Republic of Azerbaijan on the basis of national and universal values has always been at the center of the state policy as a priority direction in the activities of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev. As a result of his concept of Education, the modern education policy of Azerbaijan was carried out in accordance with the global educational challenges, the values and practices accepted by the majority of the civilized world without denying the nationwide, historical and moral factors, the progressive experiences of the previous years.

3. Heydar Aliyev's concept of education and its positive results

Heydar Aliyev, who is deeply familiar with education, all its fields and problems, made decisions in the direction of raising worthy, educated, patriotic citizens of Azerbaijan, based on the concept of Education, which he authored, from 1993, taking into account national and universal values, and created the legal basis for reforms. Thus, in Article 42 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, which was adopted on November 12, 1995, the right to education was established [URL, 1993].

In 1996, at the initiative of the Great Leader, "On Accession to the Convention of December 21, 1979 on the Recognition of Study Courses, Diplomas and Scientific Degrees in the States of the European Region", as well as in 1997 "On the Recognition of Higher Education Specializations (Qualifications) in the European Region) laws were adopted on the approval of the Convention on Recognition. This was a preparation for the gradual integration of the Azerbaijani national education system into the European educational space based on historical traditions and achievements [Aliyev, 2023].

On March 30, 1998, the State Commission for Education Reforms was established by the Decree of the head of the country. The commission was supposed to prepare the Education Reform Program in the country based on Heydar Aliyev's conceptual recommendations. The Reform Program envisages creating the education system to meet the global challenges of the 21st century, the stability and sustainability of economic development, as well as the requirements of the European labor market and ensuring access to it. On June 15, 1999 – National Liberation Day, he approved the Education Reform Program by special order [URL, 1999] and defined the main goal of the reforms. As the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev said, "using the past traditions, achievements, and great potential in the education system of Azerbaijan, the work of adapting the education system to new requirements and implementing reforms has begun, and these are also giving their positive results" [Hasanov, 2020].

This reform program, consisting of three stages, was the largest State Program in terms of duration, scope and scale.

As a result of the implementation of the "Educational innovative stage", which is the stage of the National Leader Heydar Aliyev's Education Concept in the period 1999-2003, the quality indicators of education at all stages and levels have increased, and the long-term, dynamic development of Azerbaijani education and its material and technical base has been ensured. Adapting the Education Concept of the Great Leader to modern global contexts, President of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev put forward the concept of creating human capital in order to create a new education system, including a new higher education system in the new era. New state programs related to the development of education were approved. Our national education, which provides 100 percent literacy in Azerbaijan, successfully completed its new stages: "Preparation stage" in 2004-2007, and "Implementation stage" in 2008-2013.

By having such a sensitive attitude towards the development of science and education, the great leader determined the basis of Azerbaijan's progress by paying serious attention, and this also came from the conclusion of the genius that the development of the country is related to the high education and enlightenment of people. At the same time, the national leader carried out the strengthening of the economy of our republic in parallel with the development of science and education. In other words, the path of economic development was through science and education, and Azerbaijan gained recognition and prestige in the world [Bağirov, 2022].

In our modern era, it is an undeniable fact that human capital constitutes an important part of the national wealth of every country. "Azerbaijan 2020: a vision of the future" Development Concept of the political successor of the Great Leader, President Ilham Aliyev [Azerbaijan, 2020].

"State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan", "Strategic Roadmap for the Perspective of the National Economy of the

Republic of Azerbaijan" each reflects the development priorities of human capital based on knowledge and innovation. In Azerbaijan, effective and consistent work is being done to ensure the sustainable development of human capital, to adapt education and qualified personnel training to the modern requirements of the labor market. In modern times, innovations and technologies play an important role in the sustainable economic development and productivity growth of any country. Strengthening the connection of science and education with the economy in Azerbaijan was also reflected in the "National Strategy for the Development of Science in the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2009-2015" approved by the decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated May 4, 2009. In the "State Program on Reforms in the Higher Education System of the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2009-2013" approved by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, it is noted that the progress of the society has always depended on the development of education and the correct assessment of its importance, the current demand has accelerated the development of education, scientific and technological achievements have placed more complex tasks before the educational system, which must be solved. The same document also states that the UN has declared the 21st century as the "century of education". From this point of view, the role of higher education in the formation of highly intelligent human capital and the establishment of a strong economy that creates a foundation for sustainable development is undeniable.

The "Azerbaijan 2020: Vision of the Future" development concept states that the transition from the traditional economy to the knowledge economy should be laid now, and the adequate development of human capital, which is decisive for this, should be prioritized. The urban environment prepares a good basis for the development of human capital and the establishment of a knowledge economy [Azerbaijan, 2020].

In accordance with the current concept of the development of modern higher education and its integration into the world, ADA University, Baku Higher Oil School, which meets the most modern requirements and has become a national brand, was established in Azerbaijan. Baku branches of Moscow State University named after M.V. Lomonosov and First Moscow State Medical University named after I.M. Sechenov were established. The Azerbaijan-French University (UFAZ) has started its activities in order to create an opportunity for the citizens of the Republic of Azerbaijan to receive quality education within the framework of higher education standards of leading countries without going abroad. Here, teaching in 4 majors (chemical engineering, computer science, geophysical engineering, oil and gas exploration and exploitation) has been started in English, and it is planned to issue a double diploma with the French universities of Strasbourg and Rennes 1. In recent years, the most modern campuses have been created for a number of higher education institutions, and the material, technical and educational base of all higher education institutions has been significantly updated.

Important decisions were taken by the head of state in the field of increasing the accessibility of higher

education, improving the social protection of students, training highly qualified and professional personnel in the country, and forming a competitive environment in higher education. According to the decree of the President of the country, the scholarship system has been improved, the number of scholarship places funded by the state has been increased by 16 thousand units from March 1 of the current year, and the number of students receiving scholarships is planned to be increased to 50 percent in the next two years. In addition, the amount of scholarships given to students was increased by an average of 20 percent, these measures covered more than 110 thousand students. At the same time, state-ordered places for the undergraduate level of higher education institutions were increased by 66 percent, from 27 percent to 42 percent of last year's admission plan [Bayramov, 2019].

Conclusion

The wide network of pre-school, general, vocational, secondary specialized and higher education institutions operating in our country today, and the strong scientific and pedagogical staff potential have their source precisely from the purposeful policy in the field of education carried out under the leadership of Heydar Aliyev since the 70s of the last century, and the large-scale education implemented construction has created a strong foundation for future development.

It can be concluded that the current development of our current science and education is being continued by the head of the country, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, according to the concept and system established by Heydar Aliyev. From this point of view, the integration of Azerbaijani science and education into the world, the formation of modern young personnel is a clear example of the foundation laid many years ago and the continuing education policy.

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